

NICOLAS CRITERION AND RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS

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Abstract

In this paper, we prove the Riemann Hypothesis is true via Nicolas' second criterion $\frac{n}{\varphi(n)} < e^\gamma \log \log n + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log n}}$ for all $n \geq N_{120569}$, where N_k is the product of the first k primes, P_k is the k th prime, φ is the Euler phi function, e is the Euler number, $\beta = 2 + \gamma - \log 4\pi$ and γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant.

Key words: Nicolas Criterion, Euler Totient, Riemann Hypothesis

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1 Introduction

The Riemann Hypothesis, proposed by Bernhard Riemann in 1859, is a conjecture that the Riemann zeta function has its zeros only at the negative even integers and complex numbers with real part $\frac{1}{2}$. It is also one of the Clay Mathematics Institute's Millennium Prize problems. Nicolas' second criterion states that for all $n \geq N_{120569}$, we have the inequality $\frac{n}{\varphi(n)} < e^\gamma \log \log n + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log n}}$ if and only if the Riemann Hypothesis is true [1]. Conversely if the Riemann Hypothesis is false, the inequality for the k th primorial number $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$ holds for infinitely many k and is violated for infinitely many k . So if the Riemann Hypothesis is false, there exists a large k such that $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$ for some $k \geq k_0$ and by mathematical induction, $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$ for some $k < k_0$, hence this leads to a contradiction, so the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

2 Main Proof

The Riemann Hypothesis is true if and only if for $\beta = 2 + \gamma - \log 4\pi$ and $n \geq N_{120569}$,

$$\frac{n}{\varphi(n)} < e^\gamma \log \log n + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log n}}$$

Proof:

From [[1], Theorem 5.34(1),(2)(Pg 97 and Pg 140), Lemma 5.26 and Lemma 5.27], Nicolas' second criterion is true for the k th primorial. This implies if the Riemann Hypothesis is false, there exists a large $k \geq k_0$ such that $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$. We want to show this implies

$\frac{N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\varphi(N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor})} > e^\gamma \log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} + \frac{e^{\gamma(2+\beta)}}{\sqrt{\log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}}$, where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function. Also, we need 4 lemmas.

2.1 Lemma 1

For all $k > k_0$,

$$\prod_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{P_i}\right) = \frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$$

Proof:

Let $x = \sum_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k \frac{1}{P_i}$. So $\log \prod_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k (1 - \frac{1}{P_i}) = \sum_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k \log(1 - \frac{1}{P_i}) < -x$.
Since $x = \sum_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k \frac{1}{P_i} = \log \log P_k - \log \log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$ by Merten's theorem.
So $\prod_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k (1 - \frac{1}{P_i}) = e^{\log(\frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k})} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}}) = \frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$

2.2 Lemma 2

$$\frac{\log \log N_k}{\log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}} = \frac{\log P_k}{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$$

2.3 Lemma 3

$$\frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k} \frac{\log \log N_k}{\log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}} = 1 + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$$

Proof:
 $\frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k} \frac{\log \log N_k}{\log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}} = 1 + (\frac{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\log P_k} O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})) = 1 + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})$ by de la Poussin.

2.4 Lemma 4

$$(1 + \frac{(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}(\log \log N_k)})(1 + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}})) > 1 + \frac{(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}(\log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor})}$$

Proof:

Since $\frac{1}{e^{c\sqrt{\log P_k}}}$ is asymptotically more than $\frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{\sqrt{P_k}(\log P_k)}$, Lemma 4 holds true.

Now we prove by mathematical induction that $\frac{N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\varphi(N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor})} > e^\gamma \log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} + \frac{e^\gamma(2+\beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}}$.

Assume base k is true, ie $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^\gamma(2+\beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$ for some $k > k_0$, by Lemma 1,2,3,4,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}{\varphi(N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor})} &= \frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} \prod_{i=\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}^k (1 - \frac{1}{P_i}) > (1 + \frac{(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}(\log \log N_k)})(\frac{\log P_k}{\log P_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}} + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}}))e^\gamma \log \log N_k \\ &> (1 + \frac{(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}(\log \log N_k)})(1 + O(e^{-c\sqrt{\log P_k}}))e^\gamma \log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} \\ &> (1 + \frac{(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}(\log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor})})e^\gamma \log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} > e^\gamma \log \log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} + \frac{e^\gamma(2 + \beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor}}} \end{aligned}$$

Assume the Riemann Hypothesis is false, there exists $k > k_0$ such that $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^\gamma(2+\beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$. The mathematical induction implies there has to be a time where $\frac{N_k}{\varphi(N_k)} > e^\gamma \log \log N_k + \frac{e^\gamma(2+\beta)}{\sqrt{\log N_k}}$ for some $k < k_0$. This is a contradiction because we know $\frac{n}{\varphi(n)} < e^\gamma \log \log n + \frac{e^\gamma(2+\beta)}{\sqrt{\log n}}$ for all $k < k_0$. So the Riemann Hypothesis is true and the proof is complete.

References

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